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EPIDEMICS OF CONTAGIOUS DISEASES AND THE MENTAL HEALTH OF POPULATION IN SERBIA DURING FALL/WINTER 1993 ACCORDING TO PERIODICALS: „POLITIKA“ AND „VREME“

Abstract: The general deterioration of the health of the population in 1993 in Serbia affected the entire country. As an effect of facing international sanctions, there was a shortage of doctors, medical equipment, medicines, and general funds for the normal functioning of the health system. Declining living standards, poor and inadequate nutrition and hygiene, and inadequate health care have resulted in many infectious diseases. The temptations of living in a war-torn environment and under sanctions affected the mental health of the population, which had far-reaching consequences. The paper is guided by the intention to shed new lights and give some new perspectives on the consequences of international sanctions on the health of the population of Serbia.

Keywords: epidemics, mental health, Serbia

Non MeSH: contagious diseases, sanctions

Introduction

The war that was fought in the 1990s in the area of the Socialist Federal Republic of Yugoslavia (SFRY) was the last act in the disintegration of Yugoslavia. The consequences of the conflict, which was the largest in Europe since the end of the Second World War, also damaged those Yugoslav republics and societies on whose territories the war itself did not take place. Among such republics was Serbia, where the already unfavorable political, security and economic situation was further aggravated by the introduction of international sanctions by the United Nations Security Coun-

cil (UNSC). UN Security Council Resolution 757, adopted on May 30, 1992, accused Serbia of aiding the Serb element in the civil war in Bosnia and Herzegovina (BiH). The proclaimed goal of the sanctions was to force the Serbian side to end the conflict in BiH and find a peaceful solution by combining foreign policy isolation and economic pressure on Serbia. According to the text of the resolution, sanctions against the Federal Republic of Yugoslavia (FRY) prescribed an almost absolute ban on imports and exports to the territory of Serbia and Montenegro, except in special cases such as imports of essential food products, medicines and humanitarian aid. When importing these goods, the country needed to obtain the special permit from the UNSC. Internal instability and the devastating effects of sanctions affected all aspects of life in Serbia, leading to 85% of the working-age population and 92% of pensioners living below the poverty line during the winter of 1993/1994. [1] One of the most affected parts of the system in Serbia was the national health system, in which anomalies in the form of health workers going abroad and a lack of investment in the 1980s, combined with UN sanctions, led to catastrophic consequences for the overall health of the population. The shortage of medicines, medical devices and equipment from domestic production and imports, along with poor and irregular nutrition and hygiene, are just some of the factors that led to an increase in mortality by 14.5 times compared to the pre-war period and the introduction of sanctions. [2] The lack of finances and basic resources for printing due to the import ban also had consequences for the work of the print media in Serbia. The political situation in the country also influenced the polarization of the media, which primarily consisted of a random division into 'pro-regime' and 'opposition' media. The difference of views and the division itself was noticeable in writing about the causes of sanctions in which the media close to the authorities saw the culprit in the international community's policy towards Serbia, while the media who took a different view saw the reason for imposing and implementing sanctions in the war policy of the Serbian regime. All printed media in Serbia paid great attention to the effects of sanctions and war on Serbia. Among them was *Politika*, one of the most widely circulated and oldest newspaper agencies in Serbia, which had the unofficial status of the most important and influential state-owned newspaper. Despite such a reputation, articles in this paper dealing with the effects of international sanctions abounded in a variety of analyses and reports that occasionally criticized the state's response to the new crisis, especially in the economy and health sectors. In a similar tone, the weekly paper *Vreme*, which belonged to the so-called 'independent media' established in the crisis years of the last decade of the 20th century, reported about the state of the Serbian health department in the period of autumn/winter 1993.

General health conditions

Economic sanctions, which in the second year of their implementation led to monetary collapse and hyperinflation, which remained the second largest hyperinflation in history, have significantly reduced government spending on health. Large health allocations of 15% of gross domestic product were nominally equal to pre-war allocations of only 4%. After the introduction of new sanctions in 1993 toward FRY,

the import of medical devices and equipment for the treatment of severe and chronic diseases was almost completely suspended. As one of the indirect consequences of that ban, advertisements were published in *Politika* where advertisers offered their medicines, hearing aids and organs for transplantation in exchange for money, while at the same time, pacemakers taken from deceased persons were resold on the black market. [3] In addition to the lack of equipment and medicines, a major problem was the marked departure of medical workers abroad, which affected the reduction of the quality of health services. The crisis situation in the health sector was also noticeable because the entire system was reoriented mainly to the care of emergency cases due to lack of capacity to implement preventive medical care. Inconsistent management of the crisis situation in health care has led to the decline in preventive examinations being most pronounced within vulnerable categories of the population, such as women and children, where the number of such examinations decreased by 50% compared to the period before sanctions. At the same time, hospital capacities were slightly reduced, due to which some patients did not receive adequate medical care and protection. However, the situation in the health care institutions themselves was not favorable, which resulted in an increase in mortality among hospitalized patients of 30% compared to the period before the introduction of international sanctions. [4] One of the hallmarks of the sanctions was a chronic shortage of fuel in the midst of a complete ban on oil imports, which led to the paralysis of emergency services. Most births were performed at home due to lack of fuel and irregular traffic, and at the same time, due to similar problems, doctors went on foot to visit patients.

In 1993, a sudden increase in chronic diseases was recorded in Serbia. On the other hand, some chronic patients were left without much-needed medication due to the ban on the import of drugs, as was the case with diabetics who often fell into a diabetic coma due to a lack of insulin. Due to the lack of basic medical devices such as surgical sutures, a large number of surgical procedures in the treatment of certain chronic diseases were canceled. [5] The patients themselves suffered great consequences because, compared to the available number of 900 different types of medicines in 1991, that number was reduced to 150 of the most essential ones for 1993. The number of issued prescriptions per capita dropped from 8.6 to 3, after which Serbia saw the rise of the so-called "Tabletomania" when citizens were often forced to procure necessary medicines on the black market, while thefts of medicines from pharmacies and hospitals became more frequent. The overall availability of essential medicines was reduced by 70%, while the condition of the equipment deteriorated by 60% compared to the period before the break-up of Yugoslavia. About 4,000 patients who were in the process of hemodialysis also lived in Serbia. Due to the impossibility of importing new devices for hemodialysis as well as parts for existing ones, they were used beyond all standards. While the world norm for a dialyzer was 15,000 hours, in Serbia, one dialyzer was used for an average of more than 44,000 hours. [6] Due to the lack of basic medicines and medical supplies, the work of health care institutions largely depended on donations and humanitarian aid. During the most difficult economic situation in the country in the fall of 1993, the World Health Organization (WHO) office in Belgrade demanded \$ 43,000,000 from donors for the most basic needs of the health system, of

which only 11% of that amount was collected. Difficult living conditions led to the public expression of social solidarity and humanity among the population in some cases, such as the action "Let's help each other", when the citizens of Dorćol (a part of Belgrade) exchanged the necessary medicines for months or gave them to the most vulnerable for free. [7]

The population of Serbia in 1993 lived with a quarter of the 1989 standard, while according to international organizations, 90% of citizens spent their entire income on food, and that was often not enough to meet basic food needs. More than 50% of families stopped consuming milk, while 76% of families ate without meat, which resulted in a significant lack of iron, calcium, magnesium, vitamins and biontin in the diet. [8] Food shortages in the market and general poverty, which has prevented a large number of residents from accessing basic foodstuffs, have led to an increasing incidence of anemia. The most exposed group of anemia were children in whom the lack of vitamins, milk and meat in the diet caused the protein deficiency syndrome, which endangered their overall psycho-motor development. In 1993, every second child in Belgrade suffered from anemia, while out of 70,000 students at the University of Belgrade, every fifth student also suffered from anemia. Due to food shortages, food for children was suspended in preschool institutions and schools, such as when 1,500 children were left without food due to food interruptions in preschool institutions in the city of Požarevac, which is why an action to collect aid for children's nutrition was initiated. [9] The level of nutrition, which was often below the required minimum, has affected extreme weight loss among adolescents and students, the occurrence of senility among the elderly, and reduced fertility in women. [10] Estimates of the population's diet showed that 30% of the population was starving. The food that was increasingly used in the diet was the onion, because it was affordable due to the way it was grown and the price, but also "because of the illusion of satiety created by consuming it". [11]

Declining living standards, declining quality of health care, uncertainty and political instability and the war environment have negatively affected the birth rate in Serbia. Since the introduction of sanctions in 1992, there has been a continuous negative rate of natural increase. The negative rate of natural increase was influenced by a large wave of migration from Serbia, the largest in the previous few decades. In addition, the mortality rate in Serbia was 10.2 deaths per thousand inhabitants, which marked an increase in the mortality rate for the first time in 40 years. The cause of death was mainly various diseases, especially infectious diseases. An increase in the mortality rate of 6% compared to the period before 1991 was also recorded in malignant diseases, especially bronchial cancer in both sexes equally. [12] Particularly noticeable increased mortality rate was among the youngest population of Serbia. Also, the perinatal mortality rate was constantly growing, which in Belgrade began to grow for the first time after 30 years, amounting to 16% per 1,000 newborns. [13] Infant mortality was high in Kosovo and Metohija due to dehydration and malnutrition caused by diarrhea. Such a situation was fostered by low and impoverished health care in the area, but also by insufficient health culture and prevention among the population. The ban on the import of medical equipment affected the daily activities of the Institute for Mother and Child in Belgrade, so much so that a number of children with heart problems

died waiting in line for surgery. Lack of fuel often affected emergency interventions and indirectly affected many deaths, such as when a child died in the mother's arms in the city of Pirot due to the cancellation of the bus because they had no other way to get to the doctor. The criminalization of society caused by sanctions, high unemployment, hyperinflation and war psychosis influenced the increase of violent deaths. There were cases when the theft of money, shoes or clothes often ended in death. In these killings, juveniles were often the perpetrators or victims. From the introduction of sanctions until the fall of 1993, the number of murders in Serbia increased by 100%, while the rate of violent murders in Belgrade increased so much that citizens accepted the daily news of murders as "frequent normalcy of life in the time of sanctions". Thus, the news spread almost unnoticed that the mathematician and a member of the Academy of Sciences and Arts, Đuro Kurepa, was attacked in the center of Belgrade after raising his pension, and the attackers took away two million dinars from him. Kurepa died shortly after the attack from his injuries. [14] Although the war and horrors in Croatia and Bosnia and Herzegovina distracted the population of Serbia from increasing the death rate, the scale of illness and death was such that it reached every individual, giving the impression that the disease took the form of an uncontrolled epidemic. Deaths were treated as a frequent occurrence equal to disaster.

Epidemics of infectious diseases

The events of the second half of 1993 significantly disrupted life in Serbia. The already uncertain and difficult situation in health care was aggravated by sudden illnesses from infectious diseases. Although no epidemic has been officially declared on the territory of Serbia, many indicators have shown that the spread of some infectious diseases was turning into an epidemic. Thus, in Kosovo and Metohija, there was an increase in the epidemic of infectious diseases by 20.5%, especially Hepatitis A and measles. Inadequate and poor nutrition and personal hygiene, according to *Politika*, caused more and more frequent intestinal infections, especially dysentery. [15] The emergence of contagious diseases that were believed to have been eradicated long ago worsened the epidemiological situation, taking a critical form in underdeveloped parts of the country. But some diseases, such as tuberculosis, which is one of the characteristics of poor societies, have increased in all social groups in Serbia, which speaks of the scale of the health crisis that has affected society and the state. The appearance of tuberculosis was caused by insufficient vaccination among children as well as imported cases among the refugee population. The difficult situation in the control and prevention of infectious diseases was caused by the constant influx of refugees from the former Yugoslavia, which until 1995 numbered over 700,000 people, of which about 290,000 were children. They were mostly put in collective accommodation centers that did not meet basic hygiene and housing requirements. The famine that afflicted a part of the population affected the loss of muscle and body mass, the decline in immunity, the decrease in the concentration of hemoglobin and erythrocytes, which, along with low temperatures, influenced the population to be susceptible to various viruses from seasonal flu to tuberculosis. [16] The lack of X-ray films, tuberculin, and drugs for pre-

ventive anti-tuberculosis protection enabled the rapid spread of tuberculosis. The typhus disease, which is remembered in the collective memory in Serbia as a severe and fatal disease from the time of the First World War, although it has been known for decades, has started to appear and be transmitted in Serbia again. HIV infection, which was still a largely unknown disease in Serbian society, could hardly be followed due to the lack of blood tests. The HIV virus in Serbia was characterized by a high mortality rate of 70.5% in relation to the total number of infected people. In addition to HIV, the number of people infected with other sexually transmitted diseases, especially syphilis and gonorrhea, has significantly increased.

Energy restrictions and water shortages in urban areas have accelerated the spread of epidemics of various infectious diseases. Poverty, in which the majority of the population fell, led to a significant decline in hygiene habits and the appearance of frequent skin diseases such as scabies and lice. Students who lived in collective accommodation homes were most exposed to epidemics of skin diseases, which is why at one point every third student was infected with one of the skin diseases. At the request of the students, *Politika* published a report indicating an increase in skin diseases among the residents of the "Student City" caused by several weeks of interruptions in the heating of water in the bathrooms due to insufficient quantities of fuel oil delivered to this student settlement. [17] Hyperinflation and import bans have made basic hygiene products used in the prevention of infectious diseases inaccessible. It sounds paradoxical that one toilet soap costed 30 German marks (approximately the average monthly salary in Serbia in 1993) and was more expensive than a pair of new shoes. Lack of equipment and hygiene items, as well as insufficient capacity for triage in institutions specializing in the treatment of infectious diseases, have enabled the spread of infectious diseases in hospitals and among the staff themselves. At the Infectious Diseases Clinic in Belgrade, there were the most doctors suffering from tuberculosis, while at the nearby Institute of Pathology of the Medical Faculty in Belgrade, tuberculosis rapidly began to spread among the employees. The reason for the appearance of tuberculosis among the doctors at this institute in the fall of 1993 was the lack of equipment in the form of masks and glasses and the fact that the shower cabin for disinfection was not in function. On top of that, the staff had only one lab work coat, which they disinfected themselves. In addition, due to the lack of basic hygiene items, the employees of the institute were forced to bring these products from their homes. The problem in the institute that affected the spread of the infection was the accumulation of corpses, because in the middle of the import ban for the morgue, it was not possible to procure pneumatic carts that lift the corpses into the upper chambers of the morgue's refrigerator. In addition, due to malnutrition, the workers were not able to pick up the corpses themselves, which was why a large number of corpses were placed in the corridors of the morgue during the fall and winter. On the pages of *Vreme*, readers were informed that a large number of doctors at the Institute of Pathology had tuberculosis, including one doctor who, commenting on those events for *Vreme*, said that if this and similar cases were known outside the FRY, "the whole of Yugoslavia would be quarantined". [18] The increase of microbiological and chemical pollution of water had a great influence on the occurrence of infectious diseases in Vojvodina. Bacteriologically defective water had a

share of 23% in all water analyzes. On the territory of the whole country of Serbia, infections caused by faulty water have doubled compared to the period before the introduction of international sanctions, and 15,000 people have fallen ill from them. Water treatment and disinfection was almost stopped because due to the import ban, it was not possible to import polyelectrolyte and activated carbon from France, which were used in water purification. The situation was aggravated by the fact that chlorine and chlorine appliances that were produced in Serbia were made on the basis of potassium chloride, which were imported from Germany and Israel.

The scale of the spread of infectious diseases in Serbia was large and exceeded almost all the capacities of the health system for their suppression. The biggest consequence of such a condition was high mortality. Of all the causes of death in the period of sanctions, the highest percentage of mortality growth of 141% was recorded in infectious diseases. [19] In 1993, mortality from infectious diseases increased by 319.6% compared to 1989. On the basis of autopsy findings selectively performed during 1993, it was determined that the share of infections in the total mortality increased between 20% and 42%. The number of deaths from infectious diseases increased significantly in Kosovo and Metohija and this growth amounted to 19.1%. In addition to Kosovo and Metohija, an increase in the number of measles infections was recorded in the whole of Serbia, so that the disease, for which only 91 cases were recorded in Serbia in 1991, grew to 16,777 infected in 1993. Until the beginning of the war in the former Yugoslavia, there were almost no deaths caused by measles. In Serbia, 20 people died of measles in 1993, and at the same time, one part of the children was not vaccinated due to the lack of vaccines. [20] The number of various infectious diseases and epidemics detected in Serbia was 254, not counting the influenza virus, while the total number of infected and dead is difficult to determine because due to difficult working conditions the reference institutions were not able to register all infected and deceased.

Mental health

Everyday meetings and reminders of the war environment and the devastating effects of sanctions have affected the impaired mental health of the population in Serbia. Despite the fact that in the second year of the implementation of sanctions, the majority of the population adapted to the way of life under sanctions and to chronic stress, mental states such as melancholy and apathy dominated as features of the state of their inner spirit. Due to the high prevalence of anxiety and depression, a large number of people sought psycho-social help, while a part of the population found solace in the use of opiates and psychoactive substances. The use and demand for alcohol has increased so much that a Belgrade neuropsychiatrist predicted that “many more plums will end up in alcohol than in jam”, and that this alcohol will be a particularly sought-after commodity in Belgrade where there were between 60,000 and 90,000 alcoholics, including more and more young people and public figures. [21] During the sanctions period, alcohol use increased so much that Serbia was far ahead of the European average in this aspect. Low purchasing power made access to branded and technologically correct alcohol more difficult, which led to the consumption of alcohol procu-

red from private individuals, which was sometimes defective and often led to serious mental and physical damage. Due to the ban on exports and the lack of raw materials from imports, 92% of companies in Serbia had complete or occasional interruptions in production, which is why 800,000 workers (40% of the active workforce) were sent on forced leave. Workers from urban areas on forced vacations found it very difficult to endure absence from work and lack of money, which is why some of these workers were diagnosed with depression. In Zemun's Teleoptik, *Politika* noticed a unique practice of "psychological help and support for workers on forced leave" who were threatened that "if they complain that they have nothing to live on, they will be returned to work". [22] Poverty that has affected a good part of the former so-called "middle class", in addition to social stigmatization, brought with it a sense of shame and embarrassment that led to the poor often being exposed to depression, which was one of the causes of the rise in suicides in 1993. The younger, highly-educated population and the older population were most prone to suicide, such as a seventy-three-year-old pensioner from the city of Valjevo, a prisoner of the German concentration camp in World War II, who stated in his farewell letter published by *Politika* that he was "forced to commit suicide by Serbian and Yugoslav leaders due to the famine of him and his family". [23]

Behavioral disorders were most noticeable among children, so much so that when children became ill, neurotic disorders broke out in second place in terms of frequency, which was a unique case in medicine at that time. [24] As a result of these disorders, some children became delinquents. Parents have reduced their role to a mere struggle for survival and providing the basic food minimum necessary for the family's well-being. Such a situation suppressed the development of a sense of solidarity in children, and the absence of parents caused the appearance of various forms of anti-social behavior and aggression. Doctors increasingly noticed the appearance of slow motor skills and slow intellectual development in children. [25] Chronic dissatisfaction with the general situation, but also apathy that represented an "escape from reality", spread among the student population. This led to the appearance of frequent voluntary social isolation and interruption of communication with the environment. The general disorientation of life caused by the unexpected economic crisis and the degradation of social values in the male population was in some cases manifested by going to the battlefield without any motives. The general criminalization of society was especially ingrained among the younger population, which manifested violent and destructive forms of behavior that often led to a violent death.

The social and economic catastrophe that shook Serbia severely affected psychiatric patients who did not have the opportunity to articulate their right to basic living conditions, much less to exercise it. Psychotic and non-psychotic patients who needed hospital treatment often remained outside the appropriate health and psychiatric facilities, which had a negative impact on them and their environment. On the other hand, the situation in psychiatric institutions was not significantly better either, as the phenomena of aggression, attacks on staff, destruction of inventory and escape from psychiatric institutions were more and more noticeable. Concerning testimonies about the situation in hospitals were often published on the pages of *Politika*, alleging

that in some psychiatric institutions, patients were tied to radiators due to the lack of antidepressants, or were “soothed” by ‘macolas’ - hammers weighing five to ten kilograms. [26] Food shortages also affected the diet in mental hospitals, which was often monotonous, from tea, which for months was the only “meal” for lunch and dinner at the Special Neuropsychiatric Hospital “Dr Laza Lazarević” in Belgrade, to the main meal in a special hospital for psychiatric diseases “Gornja Toponica” near the city of Nis - “soup” which consisted of water, flour and carrots. The special hospital in Gornja Toponica and the large number of deaths that were recorded in that institution in the fall and winter of 1993 were in the center of attention of *Politika* and *Vreme*. The events in Gornja Toponica supported the claims of the public that a large number of patients died in psychiatric institutions due to the lack of medicines, food, clothes and heating. The extremely unenviable situation in Gornja Toponica in November alone was expressed in the deaths of 87 patients in that hospital from hunger and cold. [27] Many infectious diseases such as tuberculosis, typhoid and dysentery also appeared in the hospital, and only after an appeal and public pressure did the Ministry of Health provide heating supplies that were still insufficient for the entire winter season. Based on some testimonies from that time, it was assumed that some patients killed each other. Similar situations occurred at the psychiatric hospital in Kovin, but also in other psychiatric institutions, where patients died from freezing, primarily due to lack of heating, blankets and clothes. The uncertain heating season forced the concerned citizens of the city of Vršac to send a letter to the world public before the winter of 1993, in which they warned that in addition to the 60,000 inhabitants of that city, 1,500 patients of the local neuropsychiatric hospital could be left without heating. [28] All the unfavorable factors that negatively affected the functioning of the health care system especially set back the level of care and treatment in neuropsychiatric institutions, which had catastrophic consequences. Compared to the pre-war period in the former Yugoslavia, the number of deaths related to mental illness has increased by 37%. Doctors and hospital staff were not able to significantly prevent the death of a large number of their patients, while they often only had to “sit helplessly next to their frozen, hungry and tied patients” as noted by Prvoslav Marković, director of neuropsychiatry at the “Dr Laza Lazarević” hospital.

Conclusion

The far-reaching consequences of international sanctions, in addition to the negative consequences for the health of the population in Serbia, also caused fundamental changes in the policy of application of sanctions by the international community. The far-reaching and negative effects that these sanctions have produced meant that this type of sanctions on this scale will never again be applied as a tool in international politics. Declining quality of life as a direct consequence of sanctions has been reflected in the emergence of infectious diseases in the form of epidemics that have often led to high mortality. When the endangered mental health of the population is taken into account in combination with all relevant indicators that showed negative tenden-

cies in the general health of the population, the questions can be asked whether sanctions endangered the biological survival of the population and to what extent did the sanctions impoverish general human physical and mental health in Serbia? Although the professional literature has laid the basic foundations for a special examination of this topic, it requires to be researched not only within historical research, but also within interdisciplinary research that will cover all aspects of this issue and include available professional literature and archives.

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